

METHODS OF TEACHING THE SUBJECT “INFORMATION AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES” IN HOSPITAL EDUCATION USING DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract. *In the given article, information and communication technologies have deeply entered the field of education at present time as well as other areas, and this plays an important role in increasing the effectiveness of the educational process and the intellectual potential of students all levels. Today, life cannot be imagined without the media, including the Internet. The novelty and uniqueness of information and communication technologies from the point of view of human development is that they penetrate almost all spheres of human activity, can be used in unlimited places and purposes. This article discusses the understanding of hospital education and hospital pedagogy, the basic principles of the hospital education system, the relevance of teaching computer science and information technology using digital technologies and their role in raising a competent generation, modern methods of teaching science, lessons on information and communication technologies in the classroom.*

Keywords: *hospital education, oncology, computer, information, digital technologies, communication tools, programming, modern teaching methods, interactive methods, online platform, computer networks, programming languages, interactive education, innovative projects.*

It is important to suggest that at present time large-scale reforms are being implemented in all areas of our country. In turn, a significant part of these reforms are reforms implemented in the education system, such as due to the resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers regarding one of such large-scale reforms, dated May 5, 2022, certain measures have been implementing in this sphere. Based on this decision, for the first time in the Republic of Uzbekistan, a state educational institution "Mehrli Maktab" was created on the basis of the Center for Children's Hematology, Oncology and Clinical Immunology of the hospital school.

Definitely, hospital education is a branch of pedagogy related to the organization of education of children undergoing long-term treatment and unable to enter an educational institution due to health reasons. Hospital pedagogy is a section of pedagogy focused on a special category of students - children in need of long-term treatment. Computer science is not like other subjects, it causes students to have a pleasant game, motivates them to reveal their creative abilities. Students become computer scientists and researchers. Based on their experience, they learn to draw conclusions and generalize.

Besides that, improving the system of training personnel in the field of information technology is one of the important conditions for the successful implementation of the strategy

Digital Uzbekistan - 2030, the development of digital technologies and ensuring their widespread implementation in the daily life of the population. The measures taken to improve the efficiency of the system of professional training and retraining of personnel in the field of information technology create a solid foundation for providing government agencies and network organizations with qualified IT specialists.

Currently, digital knowledge and modern information technology are one of the important conditions for progress. Digital technologies not only improve the governance of the state and society, but also create greater convenience for people in the social sphere.

Digital technologies are technologies related to the acquisition, storage, transmission and processing of information through electronic devices, computers, the Internet and other communication systems. Digital technologies include technologies in various fields. For example, among these technologies, one integrated chip (microcontroller) is very important. Devices created with these tickets are used to control a number of hardware such as automated systems, Internet of Things (IoT) tools. "Digital technologies" can generally be understood as consumer electronics technologies. This includes computers, smartphones, the Internet, telecommunication systems, automated technologies and a number of other technologies. Digital technologies open up opportunities for expanding the exchange of information, storage, transmission and interaction of data.

Computer science and information technology have many advantages when working with students with long-term medical needs. These subjects give students the opportunity to manage their own learning, communicate with teachers, and learn about their health.

Below, there can be observed the benefits of computer science and information technology in detail:

Online learning platforms: Students have the opportunity to manage their learning at their own time and pace. They determine the pace of learning, the choice of learning materials, and the time they spend on learning tasks.

Access to learning materials: Students have access to learning materials anytime and anywhere. This allows students to tailor their learning to their needs.

Online communication tools: Students can communicate with teachers using online communication tools such as email, instant messaging programs, or video conferencing. This allows hospital education students to communicate their questions and concerns to teachers quickly and effectively. **Online forums:** Students can communicate with their classmates and share their learning experiences through online forums. This allows students to feel less alone and find support in their studies.

Online Medical Databases: Students can use online medical databases to obtain information about their health. This information allows students to learn more about their disease and better understand the treatment process.

Online Health Consultations: Students can use online health consultations to ask questions and get advice about their health. These services help students find answers to their health problems and organize their own treatment.

Gamification: Gamification techniques can be used in computer science and information technology to increase student motivation. This technique makes the learning process interesting and stimulating.

Interactive Learning Materials: Interactive learning materials can be used to increase student motivation. These materials encourage students to actively participate and take control of their learning.

It is clear to everyone that computer science plays a very important role in the education and upbringing of children with cancer. They may find it difficult to attend school due to their physical condition, so computer science and information technology can help them continue their studies and feel socially active. With online learning platforms, children can learn from the comfort of their own home, allowing them to continue their studies and adapt their learning to their needs.

Online communication tools. Children can communicate with their classmates and friends using online communication tools. This allows them to be socially active and not feel lonely.

Online games and apps. Children can play and interact with their classmates using online games and apps. This helps them feel socially active and develop their social skills.

Online psychological counseling services: Children can use online psychological counseling services to address their psychological problems. These services help children manage their emotions and gain a better understanding of the recovery process.

Online support groups: Children can join online support groups to share their experiences and connect with other children. These groups allow children to feel less alone and find support in the recovery process.

Digital technologies can change the learning processes of students, help master the learning process. The following digital technologies can be used in teaching computer science and information technology.

Definitely, the use of digital technologies allows students to advance their learning, improve their work knowledge and productivity, develop skills, and develop creativity and thinking skills. It also provides teachers with assessment of learning, development of key knowledge for practice, individual lessons and personal support for students.

Digital technologies make computer science and information technology easier, more effective and interactive. Its use in the teaching process is important for expanding students' knowledge, increasing their motivation to learn, promoting scientific research and developing the skills needed to succeed in the 21st century.

The use of digital technologies in teaching computer science and information technology in hospital education is very important today. Digital technologies open up many opportunities for use by both students and teachers.

It can be suggested, computer science and information technology give students with long-term medical needs the opportunity to manage their learning, communicate with teachers and learn about their health. These subjects help to increase students' motivation and make their learning process more effective.

By summarising it should also be noted that computer science allows children with cancer to continue their education, be socially active, increase their motivation and receive psychological support. Learners may find it difficult to attend school due to their physical condition, so computer science and information technology can help them feel socially active and take responsibility for their learning.

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